

Air pollution metabolomic signatures and chronic respiratory diseases risk: a longitudinal study

Abstract

Background Though evidence has documented the associations of ambient air pollution with chronic respiratory diseases (CRD) and lung function, the underlying metabolic mechanisms remain largely unclear.

Research Question How does the metabolomic signature for air pollution relate to CRD risk, respiratory symptoms, and lung function?

Study Design and Methods We retrieved 171,132 participants free of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma at baseline from the UK Biobank, who had data on air pollution and metabolomics. Exposures to air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂) were assessed for 4 years before baseline considering residential address histories. We used 10-fold cross-validation elastic net regression to identify air pollution-associated metabolites.

Multivariable Cox models were used to assess the associations between metabolomic signatures and CRD risk. Mediation and pathway analysis were conducted to explore the metabolic mechanism underlying the associations.

Results During a median follow-up of 12.51 years, 8,951 and 5,980 incident COPD and asthma cases were recorded. In multivariable Cox regressions, air pollution was positively associated with CRD risk (for example, HR per interquartile range (IQR) increment in PM_{2.5}: 1.09; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.06-1.13). We identified that 103, 86, 85, and 90 metabolites in response to PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂ exposure, respectively. The metabolomic signatures showed significant associations with CRD risk (HR per standard deviation (SD) increment in PM_{2.5}-metabolomic signature: 1.11; 95% CI: 1.09-1.14). Mediation analysis showed that peripheral inflammatory and erythrocyte-related markers mediated the effects of metabolomic signatures on CRD risk. We identified 14 and 12 perturbed metabolic pathways (energy metabolism and amino acid metabolism pathways, etc.) for PM_{2.5} and NO_x-metabolomic signatures.

Interpretation Our study identifies metabolomic signatures for air pollution exposure. The metabolomic signatures showed significant associations with CRD risk, and inflammatory and erythrocyte-related markers partly mediated the metabolomic signatures-CRD links.

Key word: air pollution; metabolomic signature; chronic respiratory diseases; lung function

Chronic respiratory diseases (CRD) rank as the third leading cause of global mortality, affecting 454 million individuals in 2019 ¹. Of all CRDs, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma top the list of common conditions ², and were ranked as the fourth (COPD) and 28th (asthma) cause of disease burden in 2019 ³. Studies have also suggested that preserved ratio impaired spirometry (PRISm) is associated with respiratory symptoms and is a precursor of COPD ^{4,5}.

Ambient air pollution is regarded as one of the leading environmental factors for deaths and DALYs from CRD globally ⁶⁻⁸. Mechanistic studies indicate that exposure to ambient air pollutants may lead to inflammation, airway remodeling, oxidative DNA damage, reduced airway clearance, altered airway responsiveness, and compromised host defenses, ^{9,10} which could contribute to the development of COPD and asthma.

However, it remains unclear whether metabolic mechanisms play a role in the association between air pollution and CRD risk, as only a few studies have investigated the role of plasma metabolites or metabolic pathways on air pollution-associated respiratory conditions ¹¹⁻¹⁴. Most studies were derived from clinical settings, primarily for COPD or other CRDs. Research on air pollution-related metabolomic profiles and lung function in the general population remains relatively limited. Additionally, numerous studies concurrently assessed metabolomic profiles with health outcomes. Effectively identifying intermediate metabolites in the causal pathway and establishing the temporal sequence requires a prospective assessment of air pollution exposure, metabolomic profiles, and health outcomes.

Findings have also linked air pollution exposure to disruptions in blood cell composition^{15,16}, functioning as proxies for the hemopoietic system, system inflammatory grade, and metabolic disturbance^{17,18}. Incorporating metabolomics and specific blood markers provides a reliable approach for adding mechanistic insights between air pollution and vulnerability to CRD.

In this study, we identified the metabolomic signature for air pollution and prospectively investigated the association between metabolomic signature and CRD risk using United Kingdom Biobank (UKB) data to evaluate the long-term effects of air pollution on respiratory health. Mediation analysis and pathway analysis were conducted to investigate the metabolic pathway linking air pollution and CRD.

Methods

Data Source and Study Design

The UKB is an ongoing prospective cohort study of over 500,000 adults aged 40-69 years. The participants were recruited from 23 assessment centers, and the baseline enrollment was conducted between 2006 and 2010. The details of UKB have been previously described¹⁹. A comprehensive spectrum of data, encompassing demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral factors, was garnered from participants in England, Scotland, and Wales.

In this study, we have initially discerned a metabolomic signature profile delineating air pollution exposure within a subset of 246,947 individuals with complete metabolomics and air pollution data (**e-Figure 1**). Participants (N= 32,329) with CRD preceding the baseline and those with missing covariates (N= 43,486) were excluded from the analysis, resulting in a final cohort of 171,132 participants.

Assessment of air pollution exposure

The mean annual concentrations of particulate matter with a diameter $\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$ (PM₁₀), PM_{2.5}, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and NO₂ were obtained from the UK's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA). DEFRA provides an invaluable repository of high-resolution 1 km \times 1 km near-surface air quality data spanning the period from 2002 to 2021 within the United Kingdom²⁰. Detailed information is presented in the **e-Appendix 1**.

Considering the limitations of using baseline exposures to represent long-term air pollution exposure, our study aimed to estimate four air pollutant exposures starting from 4 years before the baseline until the baseline based on individual residential address histories and the corresponding duration of residency. The mathematical formula employed for this calculation can be specified as follows:

$$\text{concentration of air pollutant} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^j (c_i \times d_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^j d_i} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, j)$$

Where c_i represents the annual mean concentration at a specific location in a given year, d_i represents the days at that location during the calendar year, and j is the total combinations of different locations and corresponding days in a calendar year (**e-Figure 2**).

Follow-up and ascertainment of outcomes

All the participants were followed up from the initial recruitment in UKB until either the incident CRD, date of death, loss to follow-up, or the last date of follow-up on September 31, 2021, whichever occurred earlier. The main outcomes of interest in our study were the most common incident CRD (namely, COPD and asthma). COPD and asthma were identified from hospital admissions, primary care, and death records obtained from the UK National Health Service and self-reported information from nurse-led interviews.

We also analyzed cases of asthma-COPD overlap and some preliminary indications of lung function impairment, including Preserved Ratio Impaired Spirometry (PRISm) and airflow obstruction (AFO). Asthma-COPD overlap was defined as an asthma case with FEV1/FVC <0.7 and classification of airflow limitation GOLD 2+ (FEV1 <80% of predicted) at a visit. Participants with PRISm were defined as FEV1 <80% predicted and FEV1/FVC \geq 0.70. Participants with AFO were defined according to the GOLD criteria for Stage I-IV obstruction, FEV1/FVC <0.70 ²¹. Detailed information on the main outcomes and lung function is presented in the **e-Appendix 2 and 3**.

Plasma metabolites

Two hundred and fifty-one metabolomic biomarkers were measured using high-throughput nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (Nightingale Health Plc; biomarker quantification version 2020) from a randomly selected subset of non-fasting baseline plasma sample comprising 248,288 individuals from the extensive population within the UKB. Metabolomic biomarkers encompass an array of intricate metabolomic parameters, ^{22,23} including lipoprotein lipids (e.g., fatty acids and fatty acid composition) and various low-molecular-weight metabolites (e.g., amino acids, ketone bodies, and glycolysis metabolites). Details of sample collection and experimentation have been described previously ^{22,23}. The details are displayed in **e-Appendix metabolites information**.

Inflammatory markers and erythrocyte-related metrics

Inflammatory markers, erythrocyte-related metrics, and plasma metabolites were garnered from hematological assessments. The inflammatory level was evaluated by C-reactive protein (CRP) and systemic inflammation indexes, including the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), the

lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio (LMR), the platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR), and the systemic immune-inflammatory index (SII). Erythrocyte-related metrics encapsulating essential indicators of blood oxygen-carrying capacity were extracted, including hematocrit percentage (HCT), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte and reticulocyte counts, and red blood cell distribution width (RDW). The details are displayed in **e-Appendix 4**.

Covariates

A series of sociodemographic and behavioral confounders that are associated with either lung function and diseases, or ambient air pollution were considered. Data on demographics, socioeconomic factors, and behaviors were collected at baseline using questionnaires and measurements. The details are displayed in **e-Appendix 5**.

Statistical Analysis

Identification of the metabolite profiles on air pollution exposure

Before analysis, all 251 NMR metabolites were standardized using z-scores (SDs from the mean) to approximate the normal distribution of metabolite levels. To construct a metabolomic signature profile reflecting ambient air pollution exposure and preempt potential metabolite collinearity, we employed the elastic net, a regularized approach method that combines the Lasso and Ridge penalties, aiming to mitigate model overfitting²⁴. We selected the lambda, the penalty intensity parameter, through a 10-fold cross-validation process, opting for the highest lambda value that maintained a mean squared error within 1 standard deviation of the minimum. The metabolomic signature was derived by performing a weighted summation of nonzero-coefficient metabolites concentrations, with the weights being identical to their corresponding coefficients. The weighted concentrations of these nonzero-coefficient metabolites were subjected to z-score standardization after selection. Changes in the signature indicated a general escalation in the cumulative impact of the weighted sum of the selected metabolites.

We employed restricted cubic splines with four knots to visualize the nonlinear exposure-response relationship of ambient air pollutants exposure (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂) and the metabolomic signature score.

Associations of the metabolomic signature scores with CRD risk and lung function

Firstly, we examined the associations of selected individual metabolites (after natural logarithm conversion ($\ln(x+1)$) and z-scoring) with risk of CRD, lung function, inflammatory markers, and erythrocyte-related markers using multivariable linear regression. Significance was defined at a false discovery rate (FDR) of 5% using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure.

Then we used Cox proportional hazard models to examine the metabolomic signature scores-CRD risk associations. We formulated three multivariable Cox models to test the association's robustness. The first model was adjusted only for age and sex. The full model was further adjusted for alcohol consumption, physical activity, smoking status, BMI, income level, education, and occupation exposures. Finally, we added the metabolomic signature score and air pollutants to the full model. Multivariable linear regressions were also conducted to assess the association of metabolomic signature scores with lung function, inflammatory markers, and erythrocyte-related metrics.

Furthermore, to compare the strength of metabolomic signature scores-disease risk association, we also examine the association between air pollution exposure and CRD risk.

Pathway analysis and mediation analysis

Pathway analysis was conducted for selected individual metabolites derived from the optimized elastic network regression model to explore information on the complex molecule relationships and the importance of a metabolite within a pathway by over-representation and pathway topology through MetaboAnalyst 5.0²⁵. Mediation analyses were further performed to investigate whether the metabolomic signature score (exposure)-incident CRD (outcome) association could be explained by inflammatory markers and erythrocyte-related markers (mediator) with a bootstrap procedure (1,000 replications). Detailed information on pathway and mediation analysis is presented in the **e-Appendix 6**.

Stratified analysis and sensitivity analysis

To examine the robustness of the results, several sensitivity analyses were executed: (a) To conduct additional adjustments for traffic noise; (b) To define the air pollution assessment period as 3 years before baseline until baseline; (c) To consider the combined effects of air pollution on CRD

risk via quantile g-computation method to investigate the average expected change in the (log) outcome per quantile increase in the joint exposure to four air pollutants ²⁶. The quantile g-computation method produces an estimate (ψ) that represents the combined effect of simultaneously increasing all air pollutants concentrations by one quantile ²⁷; (d) To impute the missing data on metabolomics biomarkers by multivariate imputation via a chained equation.

Further analyses were stratified by age group and sex. To evaluate interactions among age, sex, and metabolomic signature score, we introduced a product term of age categories (<50, 50–60, and >60 years), sex, and metabolomic signature scores into the multivariable model. The HR with its 95% CI of the product term was employed to assess multiplicative-scale interaction.

All data analyses (**e-Figure 3**) were completed using R software (version: 4.1.2).

Results

Baseline characteristics of the study participants

Our analysis encompassed 171,132 participants free of COPD and asthma at baseline, with a mean age of 56.41 years (SD: 8.07). Among them, 86,428 (50.50%) were females. Over a median follow-up of 12.51 years (IQR: 11.63–13.22 years), participants who experienced incident CRD (8,274 cases, 4.83%) tended to be older, male, had lower levels of education, and a history of occupation exposure, were former or current smokers, and were obese (**Table 1**). Compared with the population excluded in the analysis, the population included tended to be male and had lower levels of education and abnormal BMI, and little difference was observed in other characteristics (**e-Table 1, 2**).

The mean exposures to PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂ covering the period from four years prior to the baseline until baseline were 10.64, 16.75, 31.31, and 20.72 µg/m³ (**e-Table 3**), respectively.

Metabolomic signature score in response to ambient air pollution exposure

Most metabolites demonstrated a significant association with ambient air pollution exposure. The metabolomic signature score for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂ consisted of 103, 86, 85, and 90 metabolites with nonzero coefficients derived from the optimized elastic network regression model, respectively.

The identified metabolites spanned various metabolomic classes, including relative lipoprotein lipid concentrations and lipoprotein subclass; fatty acids; amino acids; ketone bodies; and inflammation-related metabolites (**Figure 1**). Further, taking PM_{2.5} as an example, the most pronounced contribution to the positive coefficient of the metabolomic signature score came from saturated fatty acids, linoleic acid to total fatty acids percentage, and omega-3 fatty acids to total fatty acids percentage (**Figure 2**).

The positive associations between four air pollutant exposures and metabolomic signature scores were non-linear across the range of exposures to pollutants (**e-Figure 4**).

Associations of ambient air pollution and metabolomic signature score with CRD risk

In the basic model, the HRs (95% CI) per IQR elevation in PM_{2.5} and NO_x were 1.14 (1.11, 1.16) and 1.20 (1.17, 1.22) for CRD risk. Results persisted and remained robust in the multivariable-

adjusted Cox model, with HRs per IQR increment in PM_{2.5} and NO_x of 1.09 (1.06, 1.13) and 1.09 (1.06, 1.12), respectively, for CRD risk (**Table 2**).

In the multivariable-adjusted models, the metabolomic signature score was positively associated with the risk of incident CRD and COPD. For instance, HRs (95% CI) per SD increment in metabolomic signature score on PM_{2.5} exposure for CRD and COPD risk were 1.11 (1.09, 1.14) and 1.16 (1.13, 1.19), respectively. The PM₁₀ and NO_x-linked metabolomic signature scores demonstrated a significant association with incident asthma, with HRs (95% CI) of 1.04 (1.01, 1.07), respectively. Results remained robust in the mutual-adjusted Cox model (**Table 2, e-Table 4**).

Furthermore, associations of metabolomic signature scores with lung function, inflammatory markers, and erythrocyte-related markers were also examined (**e-Figure 5**). Metabolomic signature scores on air pollution exposure were positively associated with PRISm and AFO risk, specifically for PM₁₀ and NO_x.

Moreover, associations of individual metabolites with CRD risk, lung function, inflammatory markers, and erythrocyte-related markers were also examined (**Figure 2 and e-Figures 6-8**), the details are presented in **e-Appendix 7**.

Stratified analysis and sensitivity analysis

For the risk of CRD and COPD, higher HR was observed among males and individuals aged >60 (**e-Table 5**). Statistical significance was observed for multiplicative interaction between metabolomic signature score and age group (**e-Table 6**). Notably, among participants aged >60, the multiplicative interaction resulted in an HR (95% CI) of 1.14 (1.06, 1.21) on the incident CRD risk. Additionally, a multiplicative interaction was observed among males, with HR (95% CI) of 1.07 (1.02, 1.12) on the incident CRD risk.

A series of sensitivity analyses did not materially change our findings, including using air pollution exposure from 3 years prior to baseline to baseline (**e-Table 7**), and additionally adjusted for traffic noise (**e-Table 8**). The combined effect of air pollution is significantly and positively associated with CRD risk (including COPD and asthma) (**e-Table 9**). The results including participants with missing data with multivariate imputation were similar to those from our main multivariable models (**e-Table 10**).

Potential biological pathways

Our exploratory pathway analysis observed that metabolites linked to ambient PM_{2.5} exposure were significantly associated with 14 metabolic pathways, the top three including aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis (p-value = 8.85E-10); glyoxylate and dicarboxylate (p-value = 2.57E-05); valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis (p-value = 8.43E-05); (**e-Figure 9**). Metabolites linked to PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂ exposure were significantly connected with 15, 12, and 13 metabolic pathways (**e-Figures 10-12**).

In mediation analysis, we identified potential intermediate markers that exhibit consistent directions with metabolomic signature score-CRD risk association. Our findings revealed a significant partial mediation effect concerning low-grade inflammatory markers, with mediation proportions spanning 1.42% to 8.90%. The decline in blood oxygen-carrying capacity, as reflected by erythrocyte count, RDW, and Hb, also partially mediated the metabolomic signature score-CRD risk, with mediation proportions spanning 1.04% to 10.90% (**Figure 3** and **e-Figures 13-15**).

Discussion

We identified a metabolomic signature score that mirrors the long-term exposure to air pollution. Subsequently, we conducted a simultaneous exploration of the association between air pollution and corresponding metabolomic signature score with CRD, various adverse chronic respiratory outcomes, and lung function. As predicted, it was indicated that metabolomic signature score on air pollution might heighten the risk of subsequent CRD incidence and various adverse chronic respiratory outcomes. (encompassing PRISm, AFO, and ACO). Inflammation and reduced oxygen-carrying capacity played a significant role in mediating the association between metabolomic signature score on air pollution and CRD risk.

Prior studies have documented the association between short-term air pollution and the blood metabolome²⁸⁻³¹, with the majority being organic acids including tyrosine, guanosine, long-chain fatty acids, etc. Within the TwinsUK cohort, a cross-sectional study revealed associations between eight metabolites (e.g., asparagine, N-acetylglycine, and benzoate) with both long-term exposure to particulate matter and lung function³². Although there have been few studies to date that have explored potential pathways for the association between long-term exposure to air pollution and chronic respiratory diseases and lung function, our findings corroborate the results of these existing studies and extend the evidence base.

Notably, most of the air pollution-related metabolites reported previously were also included in our study, such as amino acids (histidine, tyrosine, and glycine). Among the 103, 86, 85, and 90 metabolites selected in the metabolite profile for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂, respectively, 48 metabolites were identified for these 4 air pollutants; 22 were unique to particulate matter and 18 were specific to nitrogen oxide. For example, ambient PM_{2.5} exposure exhibited a positive association with saturated fatty acids, which may promote the phosphorylation of MAPKs, intensify the activation of transcription factors like nuclear factor (NF)- κ B, and enhance the expression of inflammatory genes³³. Nevertheless, inconsistencies existed in the directions of these air pollutant–metabolite associations across studies³⁰, and these disparities may be partially linked to differences in the types of biospecimens and variations in exposure assessment approaches. Specifically, alanine was found to be positively associated with PM in plasma^{34,35}, and our study yielded results that matched these findings, but negative relations were found in serum³⁶. Air pollution-related metabolites identified above were also observed in studies involving lung function evaluation in

adult patients with COPD and/or asthma, such as branched-chain amino acids (leucine and isoleucine), citrate, glucose, fatty acids, lactate, and acetone^{37,38}.

Our study indicated that the objectively assessed metabolomic signature score was slightly stronger in predicting the risk of incident CRD and COPD than particulate matter. Consequently, utilizing the metabolomic profile may provide an objective way to capture the cumulative effect of ambient air pollution on metabolism. Given the hallmark and precursor of COPD, we extended our analysis to include PRISm and AFO and identified positive associations between them. Therefore, in the context of disease progression, our results not only highlight the metabolomic signature score on air pollution-COPD association but also its essential role in the initiation and development of antecedent diseases.

The results of pathway analysis demonstrated that air pollution exposure disturbed energy metabolism and amino acid metabolism. Glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism, glycolysis/gluconeogenesis, citrate cycle (tricarboxylic acid cycle, TCA cycle), and pyruvate metabolism are integral components of energy and carbohydrate metabolism^{39,40}. The mediation analysis results point to a conceivable biological pathway through which metabolomic signature score on air pollution elevates the CRD risk through its influence on inflammatory processes and blood cell abnormality (**Figure 3 and e-Figures 13-15**). Peripheral inflammatory markers (i.e., CRP, neutrophil count, and SII) and erythrocyte-related (i.e., HCT, RDW, and Hb) were identified, in agreement with previous studies^{18,41,42}. The morphology and quantity of erythrocytes can be affected by systemic inflammation, ineffective erythropoiesis, and nutritional deficiencies^{43,44}. Also, toxic materials of air pollutants could swiftly enter the bloodstream without undergoing prior bio-transformation, and given the frequent renewal of hematopoietic system cells, their sensitivity to air pollutants is notably high^{18,45}, which leads to impaired hemoglobin production and erythroid maturation, potentially having significant implications for cardiovascular risk prediction.^{17,43}

Subgroup analysis demonstrated gender and age differences. Gender differences could be ascribed to hormonal disparities, physiological distinctions, metabolism, and social behavior variations between the sexes^{46,47}. Age differences could be attributed to the fact that older participants typically experience age-related health decline, which might lead to a decreased biological capacity to withstand high levels of air pollution⁴⁸.

One merit of this study is the utilization of an innovative method to capture cumulative changes

in plasma metabolites associated with overall air pollution exposure through the elastic net regularized regressions innovative metabolomic signature score. Secondly, the application data from the UKB, a large-scale prospective cohort study with an extensive follow-up period. In addition, the study included diverse covariates and air pollution assessments based on residence history.

We need to acknowledge a few limitations. Firstly, data on certain variables, such as proximity to major roads and indoor exposure, were not accessible, which may confound the detrimental effects of air pollution. Secondly, some health-related data were based on self-reported information, which may lead to potential misclassification. Thirdly, given the limited proportion of follow-up data available on potential confounders, we relied on information about covariates at baseline only. Fourth, metabolomics profiling was performed on non-fasting plasma, which may pose a potential confounding effect of dietary factors on the observed associations. Finally, the metabolomic scores and respiratory outcomes were obtained from the same population and the analyses were conducted only on the same British population, limiting the generalizability of our findings.

Interpretation

In summary, in a prospective population-based cohort, we identified plasma metabolomic signature scores in response to four ambient pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, and NO₂). We provide evidence that air pollution and related metabolomic signature scores showed significant associations with incident CRD risk and reduced lung function. Furthermore, this study supports the mechanistic evidence that peripheral inflammation, morphology and quantity of erythrocytes are plausible links connecting metabolomic signature score to air pollution and CRD. Our findings suggest that air pollution plays a vital role in metabolic perturbation and CRD risk.

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Figure legends for illustrations

Figure 1. Composition and distribution of the derived metabolites.

Figure 2. Associations of the 103 metabolites constituting the metabolic signature with PM_{2.5}. Presented from up to down are the metabolites' coefficients (weights) in the metabolic signature and associations with incident CRD risk, asthma-COPD overlap, incident COPD risk, incident asthma risk, airflow obstruction (AFO), PRISm, inflammation indexes (SII, PLR, LMR, NLR, and CRP), inflammation cell, the proportions and counts of blood neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes, and platelets, reticulocyte counts, cell distribution width (RDW), hematocrit percentage (HCT), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte counts, predicted FEV₁, PEF, FVC, and FEV₁. Colors denote the association directions (red-positive and blue-inverse) and magnitudes (the darker the color, the stronger the magnitude); asterisks represent association significance (* FDR-corrected P < 0.05, ** FDR-corrected P < 0.01 and *** FDR-corrected P < 0.001).

Figure 3. The relationships between metabolomic signature score of PM_{2.5}, peripheral immunity, inflammation, erythrocyte-related measures, and CRD risk.

e-Figure 1. The flow chart of the UK Biobank participants included and excluded in the study.

COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

e-Figure 2. The air pollution exposure estimation strategy.

The participant's address is represented by colorful, rounded rectangles. Rectangles with colorful borders indicate each year during the follow-up period. Color-filled rectangles with colorful borders indicate the concentration of air pollutants at the corresponding address in the current year. The fill-in color corresponds to the address, while the border color matches the current year.

e-Figure 3. Data processing and analysis flow diagram for this study.

e-Figure 4. Exposure-response associations between air pollution exposure and corresponding metabolic signature scores.

e-Figure 5. Associations between metabolic signatures and lung function, inflammatory markers, and erythrocyte-related markers.

e-Figure 6. Associations of the 86 metabolites constituting the metabolic signature with PM₁₀. Presented from up to down are the metabolites' coefficients (weights) in the metabolic signature and associations with incident CRD risk, asthma-COPD overlap, incident COPD risk, incident asthma risk, airflow obstruction (AFO), PRISm, inflammation indexes (SII, PLR, LMR, NLR, and CRP), inflammation cell, the proportions and counts of blood neutrophils, monocytes,

lymphocytes, and platelets, reticulocyte counts, cell distribution width (RDW), hematocrit percentage (HCT), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte counts, predicted FEV₁, PEF, FVC, and FEV₁. Colors denote the association directions (red-positive and blue-inverse) and magnitudes (the darker the color, the stronger the magnitude); asterisks represent association significance (* FDR-corrected P < 0.05, ** FDR-corrected P < 0.01 and *** FDR-corrected P < 0.001).

e-Figure 7. Associations of the 85 metabolites constituting the metabolic signature with NO_x.

Presented from up to down are the metabolites' coefficients (weights) in the metabolic signature and associations with incident CRD risk, asthma-COPD overlap, incident COPD risk, incident asthma risk, airflow obstruction (AFO), PRISm, inflammation indexes (SII, PLR, LMR, NLR, and CRP), inflammation cell, the proportions and counts of blood neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes, and platelets, reticulocyte counts, cell distribution width (RDW), hematocrit percentage (HCT), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte counts, predicted FEV₁, PEF, FVC, and FEV₁. Colors denote the association directions (red-positive and blue-inverse) and magnitudes (the darker the color, the stronger the magnitude); asterisks represent association significance (* FDR-corrected P < 0.05, ** FDR-corrected P < 0.01 and *** FDR-corrected P < 0.001).

e-Figure 8. Associations of the 90 metabolites constituting the metabolic signature with NO₂.

Presented from up to down are the metabolites' coefficients (weights) in the metabolic signature and associations with incident CRD risk, asthma-COPD overlap, incident COPD risk, incident asthma risk, airflow obstruction (AFO), PRISm, inflammation indexes (SII, PLR, LMR, NLR, and CRP), inflammation cell, the proportions and counts of blood neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes, and platelets, reticulocyte counts, cell distribution width (RDW), hematocrit percentage (HCT), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte counts, predicted FEV₁, PEF, FVC, and FEV₁. Colors denote the association directions (red-positive and blue-inverse) and magnitudes (the darker the color, the stronger the magnitude); asterisks represent association significance (* FDR-corrected P < 0.05, ** FDR-corrected P < 0.01 and *** FDR-corrected P < 0.001).

e-Figure 9. Pathways analysis of identified metabolites for PM_{2.5} analyzed using MetaboAnalyst 5.0.

Only pathways with p<0.01 are labeled.

e-Figure 10. Pathways analysis of identified metabolites for PM₁₀ analyzed using MetaboAnalyst 5.0.

Only pathways with p<0.01 are labeled.

e-Figure 11. Pathways analysis of identified metabolites for NO_x analyzed using MetaboAnalyst 5.0.

Only pathways with p<0.01 are labeled.

e-Figure 12. Pathways analysis of identified metabolites for NO₂ analyzed using MetaboAnalyst 5.0.

Only pathways with $p < 0.01$ are labeled.

e-Figure 13. The relationships between metabolomic signature score of PM₁₀, peripheral immunity, inflammation, erythrocyte-related measures, and CRD risk.

e-Figure 14. The relationships between metabolomic signature score of NO_x, peripheral immunity, inflammation, erythrocyte-related measures, and CRD risk.

e-Figure 15. The relationships between metabolomic signature score of NO₂, peripheral immunity, inflammation, erythrocyte-related measures, and CRD risk.